

DiverIMPACTS
Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability

Deliverable 5.4
Guidelines for machinery requirements enabling crop diversification at the different levels of supply chain

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Executive summary

Within the DiverIMPACTS project, the objective of the Work Package 5 is to **identify the barriers to crop diversification and the strategies for moving from locked-in situations to innovations and value chains redesign**. The research presented hereby specifically targets the barriers in terms of mechanisation at the farm and downstream level.

For addressing these issue, multiple sources of information were combined including Case Studies' *Learning History*, a specific survey on machinery barriers at the farm level, in-depth analysis with some case studies, and experts' workshops (Figure 1).

The assessment provides an exhaustive view of the **machinery-related barriers to crop diversification** at the farm and downstream levels, in a variety of contexts (from niches to mainstream value chains). In total, **13 barriers are found to apply to the matter of mechanisation, of which 7 are found at the farm level and 6 at the downstream stage of the value chains**.

Barriers at the farm level are: the lack of technical and economic knowledge and references regarding crop diversification practices; the lack of resources for investing in adapted machinery; the need for further innovation in machinery adapted for crop-diversified systems; the constraints in labour organization, mental or physical load that may arise when undertaking crop diversification; and/or barriers related to the CAP, environmental or sanitary regulations. The barriers at the farm level are further analysed in the context of each type of crop diversification strategy: intercropping, strip-cropping and temporal diversification.

In particular, there is a major need for more suitable mechanisation in the context of crop diversification for strip cropping, mechanical weeding and no-tillage practices. **Two types of solutions regarding machinery innovation** were identified and are discussed. The first type of solution relies on **farmers-based innovation**. Ongoing experiments show that this approach can lead to technical solutions which suit multiple farmers and multiple crops. The second type of solution is based on **knowledge sharing between farmers and/or advisors**. Indeed, the specific machinery needed is sometimes already developed and used elsewhere. Further knowledge-related aspects are likely to help find technically and financially suitable machinery solutions (e.g., awareness of new trends and technological developments; knowledge on financial options such as co-funding). For both solutions identified, it must be underlined that relationships between farmers plays a key role. In addition to these farmers-based solutions, the agro-machinery providers (SMEs and larger firms) could play a key role by developing and offering innovative machinery.

Barriers at the downstream stage of value chains lie in the fact that the equipment for screening, cleaning, drying, storing and for processing new crops requires **further innovation and investment**. The cost and the innovation risk for actors to start-up a new value chain may therefore be high and discouraging.

The solutions identified for addressing the barriers in terms of innovation and investment at the downstream stage of value chains fall into **five strategic axes**: Developing partnership with actors of the value chains; Securing the profitability of the innovations; Limiting the cost of the investments; Seeking economies of scale; and Securing the profitability of the equipment.

Machinery innovation and funding support are requested for accelerating the diversification of cropping systems in Europe. It must be underlined that the barriers are interrelated and generally cannot be tackled separately but rather require a systemic approach. Thus, multiple actors have to be involved in the development of solutions, such as: farmers (individually or as a group); farming advisory services, agronomic R&D, agricultural education institutes; public administration & policy;

socio-economic research; banking, insurance and risk management services; downstream actors; consumers and their representatives; and civil society, environmental NGOs.

Figure 1 Overview of the sources and assessment process leading to the recommendations in terms of machinery

1. Introduction

1.1 The relevance of crop diversification in the European agriculture context

1.1.1 General characteristics of the current European agricultural systems

Current western European arable cropping systems are generally characterised by high crop yields, mid to large farms, short to medium rotations using a limited number of major crops.

In the last half-century, the productivity of European farming systems was substantially increased. The high yield levels obtained in western Europe significantly rely on fertilisers, pesticides and productivity-oriented breeding. It must be underlined that yield levels now increase only moderately (European Commission, 2018).

The observed trend in arable and vegetable farming is the scaling up of farms size (Eurostat, 2016). This trend towards bigger farms has been fuelled by bigger mechanisation. The increase in mechanisation size helped to combat higher costs levels, especially labour costs, with practically constant product prices (Van der Voort *et al.*, 2020).

Finally, the European arable cropping systems are characterized by short to medium rotations durations. Conventional agriculture crop rotations typically last only 3 to 5 years (European Commission DG ENV 2020), which indicates that a limited number of crops are cultivated. At the EU level, 70% of the annual cropping agricultural area is cultivated with only eight species (Antier C. *et al.*, *in prep.*).

1.1.2 The biodiversity challenge of the European agriculture

Within agricultural production systems, both the cultivated and natural biodiversity are important factors. Biodiversity is indispensable for agriculture, providing ecosystem services such as pollination, pest and disease control and soil and water protection.

However, the homogenisation of agriculture through agricultural intensification since the second World War has been a driving force of biodiversity loss (FAO, 2019).

In 2011, the European Union has set out a strategy to prevent the loss of biodiversity induced by increase in farm size, highly mechanized farming practices and intensified production methods (European Commission, 2011). Additionally, Bulten *et al.* (2021) also indicate that crop diversity is declining due to specialization of farming systems on a few major crops.

1.2 The roles and challenges of mechanisation and technology for crop diversification

1.2.1 At the farm level

At the farm level, mechanisation is designed and developed with a number of goals in mind. The main goal is to improve the efficiency of labour. This translates into the time reduction of operations, reduced labour requirement per hectare and the more efficient management of inputs. Another, positive, aspect of mechanisation can be the improvement of working conditions (Reid, 2011; Rijk, 1989). Reid (2011) shows that mechanisation has had the important role in the increase of production.

The current farming practices and technologies in North-western Europe are adapted for large scale farms and maximised production with a high efficiency (Bulten *et al.*, 2021). The latter report states the following characteristics which contribute to the current status in farm technology:

- Big and heavy machinery designed for efficient management of large uniform parcels;

- Specialisation in only a few crops;
- Crops are mainly sold to wholesalers;
- Outsource of field operations to contractors. Over 50% of the agricultural operations in the EU is executed by contractors (Ceettar, 2020). This includes all types of agricultural work, e.g. sowing, cultivation, fertilisation, harvesting, transport.
- Available knowledge on crop management and advice are focused on the major crops.

Furthermore, the European agriculture faces social and environmental challenges such as the unavailability of skilled workers, societal scepticism about industrialized production methods, depletion of natural resources, biodiversity loss and decreasing soil quality (Bulten *et al.*, 2021). All of these challenges may be partly related to mechanisation.

The hereby report is focused on the final challenge mentioned, i.e., to improve biodiversity by solving barriers on mechanisation. The existing developments, as described above, are affecting the further development of crop diversification strategies in European farms. The diversification strategies are in many ways a change that is at odds with current developments in farm technology. **In other terms, a significant shift in mechanisation innovations is needed to facilitate crop diversification in EU farms and have a positive effect on the agro-biodiversity.**

When looking at the farm equipment industry, one sees that market leaders are growing through mergers and acquisitions (Bjornson *et al.*, 2000) while crop diversification still remains a niche market. Currently, most innovations therefore need to come from the SME-businesses which are able to quickly pickup new market opportunities and are more innovative (Hausman, 2005).

1.2.2 At the downstream level

At the downstream stage of value chains, machinery serve for screening or sorting, drying, cleaning the agricultural production, as well as for processing it into food products, feed, industrial material¹ or energetic sources.

While Europe has a strong food processing industry, composed of large, medium and small factories and businesses, the current facilities are mostly designed in consistency with the current agricultural production i.e., for the main crops and with a high homogeneity.

For crop diversification to grow, these facilities must now be adapted or new facilities must be created for screening, sorting, drying, cleaning and processing the new crops.

1.3 The role of the technological context for supporting agro-ecology

1.3.1.1 Elements of history: how technology shaped agronomy in the 20th century

The developments in Western agriculture in the 20th century have to a large extent been driven by the developments in technology. The invention of the combustion engine, synthetic fertilizers, pesticides and developments in genetics have shaped modern agriculture to what it is today. The direction in which these technologies have developed were interdependent: for example, the genetic developments partly followed the machinery developments and the need for pesticides increased with the decreasing genetic diversity in agriculture.

The horse or ox which was pulling an implement was replaced by a tractor pulling similar machines. Almost all operations on the farm have been completely mechanized, with the tractor now providing the power and traction for their implement. For some more specific operations, self-powered

¹ E.g. hemp fibers can be processed into building material, fabric, etc.

machines were developed, like combine harvesters or pesticide sprayers. Except for the tractor, most machines are thus only used for a very limited time period in the year, which makes the investment in mechanisation for agriculture relatively expensive.

The development in mechanisation had two major interdependent advantages: its labour efficiency and its capacity. A high capacity is needed because in plant production (in moderate and continental climates) the timeframe in which a certain operation has to be executed is very limited. Sowing and harvesting are seasonal operations but even within the appropriate season there can be a limited amount of 'workable days' because of weather conditions. So a lot of work needs to be done in a limited number of days. The capacity of the machines increased over time, and with their higher capacity a farmer could handle an increasing acreage of his crops. For example, one hectare of wheat nowadays requires in total between 8 to 12 hours per ha, or in other terms, less than 1,5 hours of labour for one ton of wheat. The increasing size and capacity of the machines also meant higher capital costs for a farmer, which he had to earn back by a higher acreage, encouraging farms upscaling. Moreover, because most agricultural machines are specialized not only for a certain task but also for a certain crop, farms specialization to a limited number of crops became profitable.

Machines work very well with uniformity but have difficulties in handling diversity. For example, for sowing crops with a uniform emergence, a specific sowing rate and row space are needed, then for harvesting a uniform height, a specific plant phenotype, growth or ripening stage are also needed. This had led to development of genetically very uniform varieties. Moreover, also a uniform environment like soil, nutrients, moisture, surface are needed to efficiently use the current mechanisation. As a consequence, the developments in mechanisation led to an increasing surface of monocultures in time and space with an increasing (genetic) uniformity in terms of crop and soil management.

This increasing uniformity has consequences in terms of resilience of the system, and more specifically in terms of vulnerability to biotic stress. A well-known theory in epidemiology is that 'both the number of diseases and the incidence of disease should increase proportionally to host abundance' (Tilman et al. 2002). The pest and disease pressure have led to an increasing necessity to control them. For that purpose, chemical control of pests and diseases were used, in consistency with the monoculture and uniformity paradigm. Indeed, a large capacity is needed because pest and diseases can spread very fast in monoculture so there is a short timeframe for the application of a pesticide. Sprayers with a large capacity were developed that could quickly spray large and uniform surfaces with pesticides. For herbicides the mechanism is a bit different but the application of herbicides is dependent of a uniform crop with defined row distance; or, with the '*Round Up Ready*' varieties, a uniform resistance of the variety against an herbicide.

Also for crop protection the commonly used machinery is not optimal. The whole crop is treated with the same phytopharmaceutical product dose and the majority of the pesticide is not reaching the spots (disease lesion, insect, weed plant) where it can be effective. Similarly, preventive applications require to treat the whole crop and not only the spots the pest or disease will attack. In recent years, sprayers have been becoming a little bit optimal with the possibility of variable dosage, but this is not yet a common practice.

All these technologies for plant production have thus been developed in an interdependent way. This has led to a system with large surfaces of uniform crops that are managed with large scale mechanisation, controlled with synthetic pesticides and fertilizers and largely dependent of fossil fuel inputs. This interdependency of technologies as well as the high capital investment in the current technology makes it very hard to change this system: farmers are in several ways 'locked' in this production system.

To cut it short, in the 20th century developments in technology have very much determined the developments in agronomy. Additionally, the general paradigm was that one could control soil fertility, weeds, pests and diseases with technology while ‘ecology’ could be largely neglected (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Context of the 20th century: technology has shaped agronomy, ecology is neglected

1.3.1.2 Consequences of the 20th century paradigm and moving towards a new context

The production system described above has brought advantages in European economy. There is an abundance of affordable food available for the population. Only a small proportion of our income is spent on food². It also means that we do not have to spend much of our labour force on food production and therefore there is more time to put in other developments like science and entertainment.

However, the downsides of the current primary production system have become more and more evident the last decades. Soil degradation, declining biodiversity, greenhouse gas emissions and pollution of the environment with nutrients and pesticides have become major threats, not only for our environment but also for the capacity to produce food itself. In parallel, the growth of the world population asks for an increased level of food production while climate change is threatening the stability of food production in large parts of the world.

At the same time, there is an increasing body of evidence that cropping systems based on a high crop diversity has a large potential for a higher resource-use efficiency, higher yields, a higher biodiversity, a better soil quality and a higher resilience. Additionally, new technologies like GPS applications, machine learning, sensor techniques and artificial intelligence are rapidly emerging. These new technologies offer the chance to redesign the agricultural production system.

Machinery appears to be both a barrier and an opportunity for crop diversification. The overall challenge is to shift the direction that has been taken by machinery development (i.e., larger machinery, adapted for over-simplified cropping systems) towards a new direction, allowing for increasing local optimization rather than generic optimums, and addressing the needs of a wider diversity of crops which in turn can make the food system more sustainable.

1.4 Objectives of this research

The overall objective of the Work Package 5 (WP5) of DiverIMPACTS is to identify barriers and challenges to crop diversification, and to move from lock-ins to innovations and a value chain redesign.

This report is specifically focused on the barriers and potential solutions in terms of mechanisation and machinery both at the farm and downstream level. It aims at providing an in-depth look at the machinery aspects that can either hinder or foster the development of crop diversification in

² The average for the EU in 2019 was 13% (Eurostat, 2020).

European contexts. Recommendations are provided for making machinery effectively work for accelerating crop diversification.

2. Methodology

2.1 DiverIMPACTS' WP5 framework for analysing barriers to crop diversification

DiverIMPACTS Case Studies (CS) are found throughout Europe and vary in diversification strategies (temporal, spatial, intercropping), value chain (commodity vs small-scale, farmers' arrangements) and type of agriculture (organic, conventional).

Within WP5, the different barriers to crop diversification were identified by looking at the 25 Case Studies. Morel *et al.* (2020) show that crop diversification dynamics faces a number of socio-technical barriers along the supply chain. Of the 46 barriers identified, 13 barriers apply to the matter of mechanisation, of which 7 are found at the farm level and 6 at the downstream stage of the value chains (Table 1). It must be underlined that these barriers are interrelated and generally cannot be tackled individually but rather through a systemic approach (Antier C. et al., *in prep.*).

2.2 Methodology for the assessment of technology at the farm level

In order to assess the current status of machinery for crop diversification at the farm level, to provide orientation overcoming barriers in mechanisation, and to create guidelines for relevant innovation, information was gathered from the Case Studies.

For that purpose, data was collected from the Case Studies of DiverIMPACTS through three methods. First, all Case Studies received a questionnaire regarding the mechanisation barriers. Second, one or two Case Studies per type of diversification were further analysed (in-depth interviews, Case Studies 8, 10, 12, 16 and 23 - see highlighted in bold in the data collection chapter below). And third, Case Studies *Learning History*³ were reviewed to check about complementary information.

Finally, the interviews, the evaluation of progress reports and the examples were analysed and translated into conclusions and recommendations.

2.3 Methodology for the assessment of technology in the downstream stage of value chains

As indicated above, six barriers to crop diversification identified in (Morel *et al.*, 2020) apply to the matter of mechanisation at the downstream stage of the value chains (from harvest to retail): when the equipment for screening, cleaning, drying, storing and processing require investment and innovation (Table 1).

³ Along the DiverIMPACTS project, there is ongoing reporting from Case Studies. This *Learning History* includes the progress in the Case Study as well as barriers encountered.

Table 1 Identification of the barriers related to machinery (in bold) at the different levels of supply chain within the list of the barriers to crop diversification according to Morel *et al.* (2020)

Stage	Barrier description	Barrier code	Related to machinery
Agricultural production	Lack of technical knowledge and references	K_Tec	x
	Lack of economic knowledge and references	K_Eco	x
	Need of investment for adapted machinery	Machin_Invest	x
	Lack of technical knowledge and references about impacts on sustainability	K_Sustain	
	Profitability is low, problematic or uncertain	Profit	
	Uncertainties, risks and variability of agronomic performances	Uncert_Perf	
	Lack of technical knowledge about the impact on farming system and design	K_Syst	x
	Lack of information because of problems with advisory context	Advice	
	Current situation is still profitable on the short term	Current	
	Constraints in labor organization (period, volume), mental or physical load	Work	x
	Barriers related to CAP*, environmental or sanitary regulations	Reg	x
	Lack of adapted plant varieties in the local context	Varieties	
	Need of innovation in machinery for field activities	Machin_Innov	x
	Low agronomic performances (yield, quality)	Perf	
	Increased complexity for management and decision-making	Complex	
	Cultural barriers, confrontation with farming practices of parent's generation	Trad	
	Cognitive frame and ways of thinking need to be changed	Cogni	
	Seeds are hard or expensive to get	Seeds	
	Farmers' lack of awareness about issues linked to specialization	Awar_Farm	
Lack of available or adapted phytosanitary solutions	Phyto		
From harvest to retail	Volumes are too limited in a given area to be profitably or easily collected	Coll_Vol	
	Equipment for screening, cleaning, drying or storing requires investment	Pre_ProlInvest	x
	Equipment for processing requires investment	Process_Invest	x
	Competition on the global market with crops produced cheaper elsewhere	Compet	
	Equipment for screening requires investment	Screen_Invest	x
	Equipment for processing requires innovation	Process_Innov	x
	Regulations issues around sanitary, quality and purity aspects	Qualsan	
	Equipment for cleaning, drying or storing requires innovation	Pre_ProlInnov	x
	Administrative, fiscal or accounting issues	Admin	
	Equipment for screening requires innovation	Screen_Innov	x
Traders are reluctant to support solutions which may reduce inputs that they sell	Input		
Dealing with diversification products brings higher costs	Cost		
Market	Need to raise consumer's awareness or bad visibility of diversification benefits	Awar_Comm	
	Uncertain or unstable market	Uncert_Mark	
	No pre-existing or very limited market	Exist_Mark	
	Doubts about willingness of consumers to pay more for diversification products	Willing	
Coordination between value chain actors	No ensured and/or fair sharing of added value between actors	Price	
	No ensured or limited volumes to buy/sell products or establish secure contracts	Quant	
	Duration of contracts not enough to secure farmers in taking risks and investing	Dura	
	Limited or no cooperation between innovative farmers	Orga	
	Individualistic mentality and lack of trust between farmers limit collective action	Indiv	
	Unbalanced power in bargaining between farmers and traders	Power	
	Finding suitable contracts to address issues related to variability in production	Variab	
	Lack of communication between value chain actors	Comm	
	No ensured quality of products to be bought, sold or to establish secure contracts	Qual	
	No ensured reciprocal benefits in partnership (especially for land arrangements)	Benef	

2.4 Data collection

The options for addressing those barriers were identified through a collective expert assessment by WP5 partners⁴ of whom expertise covers a wide range of contexts. This assessment was undertaken in three steps: a. the identification and selection of a wide list of solutions for addressing barriers; b. categorizing these solutions into strategic axes; and c. matching the solutions with the types of actors to be involved for their development. Further data was collected through a questionnaire to Case Studies leaders and from the progress reports (*Learning History*) of the Case Studies.

Through these sources, insights on mechanisation challenges and needs were obtained both at the farm level and the downstream stage of value chains.

2.4.1 Case studies used to analyse barriers related to rotation extension (i.e., adding new crops)

Introducing a new crop and making an agricultural system more diverse can be achieved by strip cropping (*spatial diversification*), intercropping or lengthening the crop rotation (*temporal diversification*). In all these three strategies, the introduction of a new crop means a change in crop management and therefore on the mechanisation at the farm level.

The Case Studies having included new crops in their rotation and that contributed to the data collection are listed below (Case study number, country code, diversification strategy, value chain and type of agriculture). In bold are the case studies that were extensively studied.

- 6, CHE, Temporal, Local, Organic;
- 7, HUN, Temporal, Local, Organic;
- **8, ROU, Temporal, Commodity, Conventional;**
- 9, ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional;
- **10, POL, Temporal, Local, Conventional (Picture 1);**
- 11, FRA, Temporal, Arrangement, Conventional;
- 14, FRA, Intercropping, Commodity, Conventional;
- 15, GBR, Intercropping, Local, Conventional;
- 18, BEL, Intercropping, Local, Organic;
- 19, SWE, Intercropping, Local, Organic;
- 21, BEL, Temporal, Arrangement, Organic;
- 22, ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional;
- 24, GBR, Intercropping, Local, Organic.

⁴ WP5 partners having participated in this collective expertise include: UCLouvain; Agrosolutions; INRAE; Walagri and Wageningen University & Research (DLO).

Picture 1 An example of adding a new crop to the farming system: plantation of aronia with cabbage between its rows. Photo credit: Case Study 10

Some farms take care of more biodiversity by growing a lot of different crops which results in small acreage per crop. Examples in DiverIMPACTS show from 10 to sometimes 100 crops on one farm. This brings challenges on machinery use.

The case studies included (Number, country code, diversification strategy, value chain and type of agriculture). In bold is the case study that were extensively studied.

- 23, NLD, Temporal, Local, Organic;
- 25, FRA, Temporal, Commodity, Conventional.

2.4.2 Case studies used to analyse barriers related to strip cropping

Strip cropping describes the cultivation of different crops in strips, next to each other. As such, strip cropping is a *spatial* diversification strategy. The strips width usually varies between 1.5 and 24 meters. A major environmental benefit of strip cropping is to create a place for the auxiliary fauna and other animals to hide and seek refuge, e.g., when one crop is harvested. Additionally, the dispersal of pests and diseases in a certain crop will potentially be limited within the strip.

The Case Studies testing strip cropping which contributed to the data collection are listed below (Case study number, country code, diversification strategy, value chain and type of agriculture). In particular, Case study 16 was extensively studied.

- 9, ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional;
- **16, NLD, Spatial, Local, Organic (Picture 2);**
- 22, ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional.

Picture 2 Strip cropping in the Netherlands with different widths of strips, varying from 6 to 48 meters. Photo credit: ERF B.V.

2.4.3 Case studies used to analyse barriers related to intercropping

Through *intercropping*, farm biodiversity is increased by mixing different crops/species on the same field.

The Case Studies included (Number, country code, diversification strategy, value chain and type of agriculture) are listed below. In bold is the case study that has been extensively studied.

- 1, NLD, Intercropping, Arrangement, Conventional;
- 3, DEU, Temporal, Commodity, conventional (undersow);
- 5, FRA, Intercropping, Commodity, Conventional;
- **12, BEL, Intercropping, Commodity, Conventional;**
- 13, FRA, Temporal, Commodity, conventional (legume+brassica);
- 17, BEL, Intercropping, Commodity, organic (pea-wheat);
- 18, BEL, Intercropping, Local, organic;
- 19, SWE, Intercropping, Local, organic;
- 20, CHE, Intercropping, Local, organic.

2.4.4 Data collected from other sources

Additional data was collected from other sources such as other research projects. In particular, this allowed to gather some examples of solutions for addressing the barriers encountered. Specific solutions were identified for each type of crop diversification strategy.

3. Results

3.1 Barriers and solutions identified per diversification strategy

3.1.1 Barriers identified per diversification strategy

The inventory of barriers in the various Case Studies within DiverIMPACTS shows similarities in their nature. Overall, machinery innovation for crop diversification at the farm level is needed especially for mechanical weeding (especially for soybean crops, milk thistle, soft fruits, pea-wheat association), harvesting the new crops (e.g., hemp, flax), and more generally for operating in strip-cropping and no-tillage conditions.

However, specific barriers are encountered when considering specific diversification strategies

Using rotation extension (i.e., new crops to their farm):

- Unavailability of knowledge (Barriers: lack of technical and economical knowledge and references; lack of technical knowledge about the impact of crop diversification on farming system and design);
- Unavailability appropriate machines (Barrier: need of investment for adapted machinery);
- Investing in new mechanisation is too expensive compared to the added value with crops grown on a small acreage (Barrier: Need of investment for adapted machinery).

Specific barriers arose when cases studies decided to introduced a large number of new crops in a low acreage:

- Investing in machines for each crop separately is too expensive (Barrier: need of investment for adapted machinery);

Growing so many different crop likely result in a lack of proper machinery available (Barriers: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities; and lack of technical knowledge and references).

Using *strip cropping*:

- Adapting machine width to strip width or vice versa (Barriers: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities; Need of investment for adapted machinery);
- Using fertilization with drag hoses is difficult since crops already present on the field may be damaged in the process (Barrier: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities);
- Applying crop protection is more difficult and increases workload. Depending on the crops, spraying certain chemicals may cause problems to neighbouring crops (Barriers: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities; Constraints in labour organisation; Barriers related to CAP, environmental or sanitary regulations);
- Irrigating cannot be done for a specific strip when all crops are in place and increases workload. (Barriers: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities; Need of investment for adapted machinery; Constraints in labour organisation; Barriers related to CAP, environmental or sanitary regulations);
- Harvesting may cause continuous overloading because of inappropriate machinery and affect the neighbouring crops/strips that are still on the field (Barrier: Need of innovation in machinery for field activities);

- Using small width strips may lower work efficiency of regular machinery (Barrier: Constraints in labour organisation).

Using intercropping:

- Sowing difficulties when different sowing depths are required (Barrier: need of innovation in machinery for field activities);
- Harvesting difficulties related to the need of synchronicity or not in crops maturity (Barrier: need of innovation in machinery for field activities);
- Using different crop management practices than usual (Barriers: Lack of economical knowledge and references; lack of technical knowledge about the impact of crop diversification on farming system and design).

3.1.2 Examples of solution from DiverIMPACTS Case studies and other sources

3.1.2.1 In the context of introducing many new crops in the rotation

Two of the case studies in DiverIMPACTS (CS17 and CS23) gather a group of farmers who grow a high number of different crops, with a low acreage per crop. One of the barriers is the lack of suitable mechanisation for this type of farming. In particular, within the CS23, weed control and harvest were mentioned as the main barriers.

The problems were discussed between farmers gathered in this CS. A tour of farms and on-farm discussions led to many practical tips and ideas to reduce manual labour. The group also researched options presented on trade fairs, such as the Biomechatech fair. There, the farmers learned about the weed control robots that are in development. The development will probably take a few years and therefore it is not a short-term solution. The farmer group within CS23 also concluded that better knowledge on mechanical weed control would help increase efficiency of the operation and reduce manual labour input at a later time. Especially setting up the machine and choosing the right time to carry-out the activity can help prevent manual labour input. For that purpose, a demonstration is being organised for training the farmers in setting up the weed control machine.

This practical knowledge transfer about weed control could be an example to make better use of the available mechanisation, increase efficiency and reduce manual labour input.

3.1.3 In the context of strip-cropping and intercropping: harvesting machinery

One of the challenges encountered in the context of strip-cropping is to harvest crops without driving over the adjacent crop(s). Some initiatives in the Netherlands provide an example of solution in this regard.

Within the Dutch research project SMARAGD, a group of farmers⁵ with fixed traffic lanes started to discuss the requirements and wishes they had regarding the challenges of harvesting in the context of strip-cropping. In order to make the discussion easier, the activity of the harvest was broken down in the successive steps and each step was then individually discussed.

Farmers came up with the idea of combining a *Windrower* and a bunker harvester, with the additional requirement that the overall weight would not be too high in order to reduce soil compaction. The goal was therefore to keep machines as small and light as possible. Another requirement was to use

⁵ The group of farmers included for example the 'Boerderij van de toekomst' (Farm of the Future) and 'Akker van de Toekomst' initiatives. Both initiatives focus on strip-cropping with 3.15 meters wide fixed traffic lanes (*controlled traffic farming*); in every strip a different crop is grown.

existing mechanisation in order to have a quick and affordable solution. In the end, the solution found for the harvest was as follows:

- a 4-row of 3 meters-wide *Windrower* to harvest the root crops (e.g., potatoes and onions) and place the production on the field;
- a 1/2-row of 1.5 meter off-set trailed bunker harvester for loading the crops with a special axle to fit the track width of 3.15 meter;
- unloading is done on the headland.

Within the SMARAGD project this option was called a *Farmer Smart option*. Indeed, the main options were derived from the wishes of farmers and also solved by farmers (Van der Voort et al., in prep.).

This harvest method has multiple benefits. First, the solution can be used to harvest multiple crops. Farmers could harvest potatoes, onions and beetroot with the harvest solution. The second benefit is that the solution is cost-efficient as it is based on existing mechanisation (adapted here with a special axle). The third benefit is that the solution prevents from using high total machine weight, especially of the bunker harvester.

When different harvesting technologies were assessed in terms of technical and economic performance⁶ in the context of the SMARAGD project, this option was ranked as highly cost-efficient (Van Dalssen et al., 2021).

Here, the discussion and exploration with the group of farmers of their requirements and wishes for harvesting machinery in the context of their strip cropping systems resulted in a suitable and relatively inexpensive solution that fits multiple crops. This approach for elaborating solutions for addressing the problems encountered by farmers could also be implemented by Case Studies. The solution identified could also be directly copied when the same crops are involved.

Another example is within an American initiative, *Constant canopy crops*, offering the following solution: for combined crops (intercropping), a practical solution is to harvest with *Flexxifinger's Flexxiselect* to harvest only wheat (or grain crops) and protect the other crop from being harvested as well (e.g., it protects the pulses during the harvest of cereals). The solution is specially developed for intercropping and fits to the header of a combine harvester.

3.1.4 In the context of strip-cropping: ploughing machinery

Another interesting example within the SMARAGD project is the development of a plough specifically relevant for strip cropping by a SME-business (*Steверink Techniek*). The unique aspect of the plough is that no furrow is left behind. As a consequence, a strip can be ploughed instead of the whole field. This specific solution also benefits the weed management and soil fertility aspects in strip-cropping systems. The plough is specifically designed with strip cropping in mind and is for sale in different working width, as they can vary from one cropping system to another.

3.2 Barriers and solutions identified at the farm level

3.2.1 Barriers identified at the farm level

Table 2 Summary of the insights regarding machinery barriers at the farm level obtained via the *Learning History* of the Case Studies.

Case study	Case study characteristics (Country code, type of diversification, type of innovation)	Insights on mechanisation challenges and needs at the farm level
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⁶ In the assessment of the economic performance the machine, energy and labour costs were included.

	setting, conventional or organic agriculture)	
CS1	NLD, Intercropping, Arrangement, Conventional	The hired contractors are looking for ways to adapt machinery for better soil preservation.
CS3	DEU, Temporal, Commodity, conventional	The farmers are looking for suitable mechanisation for sowing in a no-tillage cultivation system.
CS7	HUN, Temporal, Local, Organic	Need for special weeding machines for soybean cultivation; Lack of availability of machines during harvest as the harvest times coincided with other, more common, crops.
CS9	ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional	No fully adapted machinery for harvesting hemp, especially in the context of strip cropping.
CS10	POL, Temporal, Local, Conventional	Lack of availability of machinery for harvesting flax; No adapted machinery for mechanical weeding in milk thistle and soft fruits: weeds cause lower yields in the mentioned crops.
CS11	FRA, Temporal, Arrangement, Conventional	
CS12	BEL, Intercropping, Commodity, Conventional	Need for investment in specialized machinery for no-tillage and diversification.
CS16	NLD, Spatial, Local, Organic	The need for suitable mechanisation for strip cropping.
CS17	BEL, Intercropping, Commodity, organic	Looking for mechanical weeding machinery to reduce dependency on herbicides (pea-wheat).
CS18	BEL, Intercropping, Local, organic	
CS19	SWE, Intercropping, Local, organic	
CS20	CHE, Intercropping, Local, organic	Need for adapted mechanisation for tillage and weed control.
CS22	ITA, Spatial, Local, Conventional	New mechanisation needed for strip cropping in general.
CS23	NLD, Temporal, Local, Organic	Need for harvesting machinery specifically adapted for a high number of crops with low acreage; Need for mechanical weed control to reduce manual labour inputs (special focus on improving working conditions).
CS25	FRA, Temporal, Commodity, Conventional	Low-mechanized cultivation leads to high manual labour costs and therefore high production costs in general.

The main barrier observed is the need for innovation in machinery for field activities (Table 2). For a number of aspects, no machinery solutions are already available. This applies to all farming operations (sowing, ploughing, controlling weeds, harvesting, etc.). It must be underlined that in some cases, there are solutions available, but they might still not be known by farmers and advisors or be too costly for the intended goal.

The second barrier observed is the need of investment for adapted machinery (Table 2). Indeed, the required investment in mechanisation is contradictory to a number of different aspects, such as the low acreage of crops and/or the low number of crops on which the mechanisation can be deployed.

Other barriers observed are work planning; regulations; and knowledge on technical, economical aspects and on farming systems and design.

The *work* barrier mainly highlights the constraints in labour organisation (period, volume) due to the diversification - for example, when harvest machinery is available but there is no room in the planning of the harvest period for additional crops (Table 2).

The barrier on *regulations* is mainly related to the environmental or sanitary regulations - for example the use of crop protection in strip cropping is very specific and doesn't fit the current regulation.

Finally, the barriers on *Knowledge* are related to a lack of knowledge and references on the subject in question. Additional information on economics, mechanisation / technology and on farming systems and design are relevant to farmers for undertaking crop diversification (Table 2).

The main themes of the barriers observed are mechanical weeding, strip cropping, harvesting, no-tillage, crop protection and irrigation.

- Most barriers apply to the matter of mechanical weeding. Mechanical weeding appears to be an issue in all types of diversification. The main barrier is that the mechanisation is not suited for the spatial diversification or for the new crop introduced. Therefore, innovation and/or investment are needed to resolve this issue;
- Strip-cropping requires all mechanisation to fit the strip width. Therefore, multiple barriers apply to strip-cropping. This also apply to the irrigation and crop protection matters;
- The harvesting machinery is a major theme. Strip-cropping and intercropping requires specific, innovative harvesting machinery. In temporal diversification or when a high number of crops are grown with low acreage, the challenge is that the mechanisation is not suitable to harvest different crops, which indirectly results in the need for investment;
- The no-tillage systems require specific innovation and investments related to mechanisation. Seeding is a main challenge;
- The crop protection and irrigation matters relate to the differences in crop needs and their spatial arrangement. This requires adaptations in mechanisation or investment is suitable mechanisation.

The barriers observed through the questionnaire, in-depth interviews and Case Studies' Learning History are similar with the barriers identified by (Morel *et al*, 2020) and are also consistent with other research (Van Loon *et al.*, 2020; Rijk, 1989; Curfs, 1979). There were no additional barriers found.

There is a mismatch in the economy of scale of the mechanisation size compared to the farm size. Within the European Case Studies, the mismatch is not necessarily a farm size issue, but more often a field size or a spatial distribution issue. A number of Case Studies indeed indicated that the machinery options do not fit the strip or intercropping practices applied at a smaller scale, due to the crop diversity.

In particular, in strip cropping, the strip width and the fact that during harvest there still is a neighbouring crop in the next strip, lead to a mismatch in mechanisation size or design.

Still, as the examples cited above show, specific solutions can be developed for harvesting, ploughing and irrigation in the context of strip cropping. The potential solutions can be found either in technology (e.g., drip irrigation, harvest with *Flexxifinger Flexxiselect* in intercrops,) or in the farming design itself (e.g., a "service crop" strip such as grass-clover can be introduced to accommodate transport units during harvest, e.g., CS16).

Second, costs of machinery is also an important barrier. Most case studies mention a need to change or replace mechanisation, or the need for new mechanisation in case of new crops. This leads to similar or higher mechanisation costs compared to their other, more common crops. While the crop diversity lies in a lower acreage, economies of scale are limited, so the total production cost rises. This leads to a competitive disadvantage further in the supply chain (see barriers related to price for diversified cropping systems in (Amrom *et al.*, in prep)). This situation also leads to additional working hours needed for the same activities, which further weigh in the total production cost.

One of the potential solutions for addressing the machinery cost problem is to involve a mechanisation supplier when planning to introduce a new crop: the supplier may rent the mechanisation needed or provide financial solutions to overcome the initial investment costs. Another option is to start cultivating a new crop in collaboration with other farmers, the investment being then split between the farmers.

Finally, the capacity to operate, maintain and repair the equipment can be a challenge. The capacity is here defined not only in terms of the number of people available but also in terms of the knowledge available. As an example, within the CS23, farmers indicated they face a barrier for mechanical weed control. Here the challenge is not the machine availability, but the capacity to setup their machine consistently as well as to understand at which moment it is best to use it for efficient weed control.

Related to this barrier is the declining number of herbicides available for conventional farming (Bleeker, n.d.), increasing the need for mechanical weed control.

3.2.2 Solutions: Technology supporting agro-ecology, chances for a new paradigm in the 21st century

Machinery is central in farming system. It, directly or indirectly, affects soil management practices, pesticides and fertilisers application methods, fossil fuel use, and orientate the choice of cropping systems by farmers.

All these aspects must also be considered central for rethinking agriculture towards more sustainability. Regarding soil management, innovative practices like reduced tillage, controlled traffic, organic fertilisation, and decreasing axle loads can improve the soils ecological services (water regulation, biodiversity and carbon sequestration). Significant reductions in pesticide use can also be accomplished by increasing the precision of the pesticide application through innovative machinery and technology. There is an increasing body of evidence that cropping systems with a high crop diversity have a large potential for a higher resource use efficiency, higher yields, a higher biodiversity a better soil quality and a higher resilience (Beillouin *et al.*, 2019). Last but not least current agriculture has become largely dependent of fossil fuels while at the same time farms have ample opportunities to produce renewable energy.

Crop diversity, sustainable soil management, precise application of inputs like pesticides and fertilisers, multifunctional land use care for biodiversity, and reduction of fossil fuel use are asking for another type of technology in agriculture than currently available.

Figure 3 21st century: Technology is inspired by ecology and supports agro-ecology.

Contrary to the 20th century situation where technology determined the way we produced food and left ecology out of the equation, **technology should now take ecology into account, should be inspired by ecology and should support agro-ecology** (Figure 3). Technology should be able to deal with diversity instead of creating uniformity and technology should not destroy biodiversity but enhance it. It is questionable whether we can build on the traditional technology like pesticides, synthetic fertilisers and the fuel-powered tractors with an implement behind it, or develop a whole new technology system, or develop a hybrid of old and new⁷.

Regarding the options for technological developments *fitting the new paradigm*, new technologies like GPS applications, machine learning, sensor techniques and artificial intelligence are rapidly emerging. It must be underlined that these new technologies have until recently only marginally been applied in open field plant production⁸.

Some applications have been introduced as add-on to the conventional technology. For example, the (RTK-) GPS system for tractors was a kick start for various precision farming applications and made *Controlled Traffic Farming (CTF)* quite easily applicable (Picture 3). CTF reduces soil compaction and can improve resource use efficiency because of the better soil quality. Moreover because of the fixed traffic lanes, precision applications of pesticides or fertilisers are easier to apply. GPS and sensor applications are also implemented in large scale spraying machines which makes variable dosage possible and in time it might lead even to individual plant treatment. Specifically, regarding crop diversification, controlled traffic systems combined with GPS applications also make strip cropping much more feasible (Picture 4). Parties such as *Agrolntelli*, *Naio*, *Odd.Bott* and *Ecorobotics* are developing automated solutions for weed control. These automated or robotic initiatives with small and light mechanisation fit within the premises of technology supporting agro-ecology.

⁷ Another alternative to adapting our technology would be to reintroduce a large amount of manual labour in agriculture instead of chemical, fuel-based and technological solutions, but this option might be socially and economically not feasible. Thus we here focus on technological innovation.

⁸ In comparison, they already are more commonly used in glasshouse production and dairy farming, e.g. in climate control milking and milking robots

Picture 3 Controlled traffic farming with the use of RTK-GPS and tracks. Photo credit: Wageningen University & Research.

Picture 4 Strip cropping systems combined with non-trafficked cultivation beds and controlled traffic lanes. Photo credit: Wageningen University & Research.

However, the applications described above are still building on the traditional technology with some add-ons. It combines the available technology with the challenges in soil management and spatial crop diversity. These machines are still conceived for large scale farming and need a driver. Other examples of innovative machinery include *WecoDyn* and *Oekosem Rotor-Strip-Till*. *WecoDyn* is an all-in-one system for combined passes. *WecoDyn* has nine main tools. It can be used for combined 3D-seeding (direct seeding, seed drilling, band and wide sowing) with up to three different seeds or fertilizers as well as for pure tillage. The *Oekosem Rotor-Strip-Till* process creates a perfect seedbed for all cultivation in rows in a single pass. The unprocessed strips protect against erosion and store water. The machine allows to fertilize, loosen the soil and sow, all in a single pass. This saves time and money, and maintains the strong yield capability of the ground.

More innovative developments however are going towards hands-free cultivations. The large machines with a relatively high axle loads are replaced by small autonomous machines that make use of sensors, camera imaging, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and renewable energy. A few examples of

the combination of some of these techniques are already available on the market, such as the *Ecorobotix* (Picture 5). *Ecorobotix* is an autonomous machine designed for weed control. The robot works on solar energy, distinguishes weed plants from culture plants and puts a drop of herbicide on the weed. The same principle could be applied to mechanical weeding, control of fungal diseases and control of pests. Farm operations that can be executed by robots also include seeding and planting of crops (see The Farm of the Future initiative in Lelystad, Netherlands). These robot techniques combine very well with the strip-cropping systems applied at the Farm of the Future.

Picture 5 Left, the *Ecorobotix* for weed control in sugar beets, right the *AgroIntelli*, hoeing in strip cropping in cabbage. Photos credits: left: *EcoRobotix*; right: Wageningen University & Research

Finally, other techniques such as the development of drones and remote sensing offer great opportunities to deal with diversity in agriculture. Even the first machines for the cultivation of complete crop mixes (pixel cropping) are already available. All these techniques open new windows of opportunity for applying crop diversity in European fields.

3.3 Barriers and solutions identified at the post-harvest and processing stage

Barriers identified at the post-harvest and processing stage are mentioned in Table 2 and Table 3.

3.3.1 Solutions identified for overcoming machinery barriers

In total, 13 solutions were identified for addressing the machinery-related barriers to crop diversification at the downstream stage of value chains (see A1 to E6 in

Table 3). The solutions identified fall into five strategic axes:

- Developing partnership with actors of the value chains; (2 solutions);
- Securing the profitability of the innovations; (1 solution);
- Limiting the cost of the investments; (3 solutions);
- Seeking economies of scale; (2 solutions); and
- Securing the profitability of the equipment. (5 solutions).

3.3.2 Actors to be involved in each solution

The actors to be involved in the development of each solution were identified (See Table 4 in appendix).

They include: farmers (individually or as a group); farming advisory services, agronomic R&D, agricultural education institutes; public administration & policy; socio-economic research; banking, insurance and risk management services; downstream actors; consumers and their representatives; and civil society, environmental NGOs.

Table 3 List of the solutions to machinery-related barriers to crop diversification at the downstream stage of value chains, identified through the collective assessment by WP5. Adapted from (Amrom et al. 2021).

Barriers	Strategic axes	Solutions
Equipment for screening, cleaning, drying, processing needs innovation (Process_innov_Pre-Proinnov, Screen-Innov)	Developing partnerships	A1 Partnerships at the value chain level, from the farm to the processing stages, to co-adapt the processing (eg. compromise on a variety that is both adapted to the local context and adapted to the processing).
		A2 Partnerships of several processing actors for collective innovation in terms of equipment.
	Securing the profitability of the innovation	B1 Pricing system/incentives that ensures a sufficient return on investment for stakeholders involved in the innovation.
Equipment for screening, cleaning, drying, storing and processing requires investment (Pre_Proinvest; Screen-Invest; Process_invest).	Limiting the cost of investment	C1 Collective purchase of processing equipment is identified as a good way to split the invest cost and obtain better profitability (in regard to the cost/benefit ratio) and have an appropriate sizing of the equipment for the amount of products.
		C2 Collective purchase may also allow splitting the necessary organizational and technical skills development.
		C3 Providing financial support (subsidies, incentives) for diversified crops' innovative processing equipment.
	Seek economies of scale	D1 Increase the volume of production of the crop to be processed.
		D2 Increase in the number of crops concerned by the new equipment.
	Securing the profitability of the equipment	E1 Focus on equipment that offer an significant added value to the product.
		E2 Selling screening, cleaning, drying, storing and processing services to other actors if the equipment is not used at 100% of its capacity.
		E3 Long-term contracts for the processed products.
		E4 Diversifying the marketing opportunities.
		E5 Pricing system/incentives that ensures a sufficient return for stakeholders investing on the new equipment.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

4.1 At the farm level

4.1.1 Conclusions

Crop diversification appears to be hindered by mechanisation issues in most of the case studies (CS). Indeed, we demonstrate that historical developments in agriculture such as specialisation, i.e., larger farms or uniform parcels growing fewer crops, has led to a system encouraging simplification rather than diversification in agriculture.

The main barriers found were:

- The need for innovation in machinery for field activities

The farm equipment available does not fit all of the needs of the farmers in the context of more diverse cropping systems.

In some cases, are examples of potential solutions available, including technological solutions; innovation approaches at the farm level (such as the *Farmer Smart solution*); and changes in the method of cultivation or the design of the cropping system. Even when solutions are available, they might not be known by farmers and advisors.

Most significantly, the main themes that are not covered are mechanical weeding, harvesting, strip-cropping and no-tillage. Developing new machines or adapt current machines will be necessary to create good solutions for diversified cropping systems, and could turn to be market opportunities for machinery manufacturers.

- The need for investment in adapted machinery

In most cases, the diversification requires additional or adapted mechanisation. The costs of mechanisation are therefore another barrier to diversification. In many CS, the farmers and/or initiatives start with a low acreage, which makes investments in mechanisation heavily weigh on the introduced crops.

- Knowledge

Three barriers related to knowledge were found at the farm level: the technical, economical and farming systems aspects. There are some practical examples from the CS to address the knowledge gap. One of the most effective ways is to create farmer groups. In one of the examples a group of farmers had a brainstorm with technical manufactures and researchers. Further communication should be undertaken on solutions developed in CS or elsewhere, in order to ensure that other farmers can learn or buy the solutions developed.

- Other aspects

When solutions for addressing the barrier exist, they might have negative side effects such as lower efficiency, constraints in labour organisation, increased workload, and thus increase the production costs. This increase in production costs is not compensated as there are no (or only limited) additional revenues for products cultivated in a more agro-ecological way through crop diversification, as reported in other reports of DiverIMPACTS (REF).

Another organizational barrier was the availability of mechanisation (i.e., when the machines exist but are not available at harvest time).

The environmental and/or sanitary regulations may also constitute a barrier: the crop protection application in diversified cropping systems is quite different while current rules and regulations are based on the mainstream method of cultivation.

4.1.2 Recommendations

Within DiverIMPACTS, solutions to address the barriers were reported (Amrom et al., 2021). The solutions are taken as reference for the recommendations.

- Machinery innovation and investment

The solutions regarding machinery innovation are based either on the adaptation of the existing machines to the new cultivation methods, or the other way round i.e., adapting the cultivation system to the existing machines available. As an example, an analysis of the mechanical weeding options shows that both the adaptation of the system to the existing mechanisation and the flexibility of machines to the different crops are relevant.

An important prerequisite is the insight in the potential market demand for such a new or adapted machine. The manufacturer could be stimulated in the development if a bigger demand is identified within the country or at the European level.

Further research is recommended regarding the agrotechnology infrastructure, as it varies significantly across countries. Special attention should be given to the capacities of SME-businesses for innovating towards crop diversification. As an example, in the Netherlands, there are a significant number of SME-businesses which focus on designing and developing new mechanisation for agriculture. These businesses fill the gap that the large manufacturers leave open. Their capacity for innovation, combined with a fine network of dealers, who in some cases are able to adapt new or second hand mechanisation to the needs of customers, create an environment in which solutions can potentially be solved more quickly. Such an environment could be nurtured further with stimulus and policies.

- Knowledge

The development of further knowledge and strengthening the accessibility and distribution of the knowledge available are the two main strategies. In both cases a number of different Horizon 2020 projects could be helpful to address the knowledge issue, e.g., Nefertiti project which seeks to develop a EU-wide network of demonstration and pilot farms, designed to improve knowledge transfer within the agricultural community and sector.

- Other recommendations

As the mechanical weed control is a barrier in numerous Case Studies, further research in mechanical weed control could potentially lead to a bundling in demand towards manufacturers. This could help farmers, but also manufacturers secure sufficient demand for the adaptation of current machines or development of new machines.

Overall, the development of new technologies could be beneficial to crop diversification, especially if *ecology* and *agronomy* are a central to the development process.

4.2 At the post-harvest and processing levels

The solutions identified for addressing the barriers in terms of innovation and investment fall into five strategic axes:

- Developing partnerships, bringing actors of the value chains together;
- Securing the profitability of the innovations;

- Limiting the cost of the investments;
- Seeking economies of scale; and
- Securing the profitability of the equipment.

5. Partners involved in the work

The current report mainly involved DLO and UCL partners, and more secondarily other DiverIMPACTS partners. Contributions are listed below.

Methodology conception and data collection, data analysis, report redaction: DLO (farming topics) and UCL (downstream topics).

Collective expert assessment: UCL, DLO, INRAE, Agrosolutions, Walagri, Baertschi.

Report review: INRAE.

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7. Appendix

Table 4 Solutions identified to overcome machinery-related barriers to crop diversification from harvest to retail

Solutions	Farmers	Advisory, Extension services; Agronomic R&D; Agricultural Education	Public Administration & Policy	Socio-eco Research	Banking/ Insurance/ Risk management	Downstream actors	Consumers and their representatives	Civil society, environmental NGOs
A1 Partnerships at the value chain level, from the farm to the processing stages, to co-adapt the processing equipment	x	x		x		x		
A2 Partnerships of several processing actors for collective innovation in terms of equipment	x	x			x	x		
B1 Pricing system/incentives that ensures a sufficient return on investment for stakeholders involved in the innovation	x		x	x		x	x	x
C1 Collective purchase of processing equipment is identified as a good way to obtain better profitability (in regard to the cost/benefit ratio) and have an appropriate sizing of the equipment	x	x			x	x		
C2 Collective purchase may also allow splitting the necessary organizational and technical skills development.	x	x				x		
C3 Providing financial support for diversified crops' innovative processing equipment	x		x		x	x		

Table 4 (bis) Solutions identified to overcome machinery-related barriers to crop diversification from harvest to retail

Solutions	Farmers	Advisory, Extension services; Agronomic R&D; Agricultural Education	Public Administration & Policy	Socio-eco Research	Banking/ Insurance/ Risk management	Downstream actors	Consumers and their representatives	Civil society, environmental NGOs
D1 Increasing the volume of production of the crop to be processed	x	x			x			
D2 Increasing the number of crops to which the new equipment may apply	x	x			x			
E1 Focus on equipment that offer a significant added value to the product	x	x				x		
E2 Selling screening, cleaning, drying, storing and processing services to other actors if the equipment is not used at 100% of its capacity	x	x				x	x	
E3 Long-term contracts for the processed products	x	x	x	x		x		
E4 Diversifying the marketing opportunities	x					x	x	
E5 Pricing system/incentives that ensures a sufficient return for stakeholders investing on the new equipment and practices	x		x	x			x	x

Notes: Solutions A1 to B1 address the barriers in terms of innovation for the equipment for screening, cleaning, drying, processing (barriers *Process_innov_Pre-Proinnov*, *Screen-Innov*) while solutions C1 to E6 address the barriers in terms of investment. These solutions can be categorized into strategic axes (see Table 3). The identification of actors is adapted from (Amrom et al. 2021). upstream actors are not mentioned here.